

Loneliness as an interface between AD and suicidal behavior.

Loneliness has been shown to be an isolated factor associated with AD (OR=1.89 [CI:1.69-1.82]) and suicidal behavioral (OR=2.29 [CI:2.07-2.53]). At the interface between both illnesses, loneliness was strongly associated with hopelessness($r=0.628$), entrapment($r=0.466$), insomnia($r=0.519$), and stress($r=0.474$).